

THE DEVELOPMENT PATHWAY OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE THROUGH CONTEXTUAL INSTRUCTION IN ENGLISH*

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Abstract

This article examines the development pathway of communicative competence (CC) in English through contextual instruction (CI). Drawing on Trevor Doyle's learner-centred framework and the contextualization–decontextualization–recontextualization (CDR) principle, the paper proposes a cyclical eight-stage framework comprising: student database, content with language focus, setting learning intentions, text and context selection, prior knowledge activation, learning strategy development, collaboration, and authentic assessment. Each stage is analysed in terms of its pedagogical implications and contribution to fostering autonomous, competent users of English in academic, professional, and global contexts. The Whole–Part–Whole model, the REACT strategy, and the Gradual Release of Responsibility model are integrated as core methodological tools supporting contextualised language learning. To enhance the practical relevance of the framework, the article also presents findings from a pilot quasi-experimental study, which provided preliminary evidence of the pathway's effectiveness in supporting the development of students' communicative competence in English.

Key words: *Communicative competence, Contextual instruction, Contextualization, Decontextualization, Recontextualization, Learner autonomy, Authentic assessment.*

1. Introduction

In the era of accelerated globalization, communicative competence in English has acquired the status of an essential skill for the contemporary individual. Communication increasingly transcends geographical and cultural boundaries, and the

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ability to use English effectively in diverse social and professional contexts has become a prerequisite for personal and professional success. In response to these challenges, the process of teaching-learning-assessment of English has evolved significantly over recent decades, adapting to the complex demands of a global society.

Contextualised Instruction (CI) has emerged within this framework as a promising educational paradigm, with the potential to transform how learners acquire and develop Communicative Competence. Unlike traditional approaches focused on isolated grammar and vocabulary, CI promotes learning and using language in authentic contexts – whether in business, medical, or everyday settings. This approach aims to develop integrated skills: listening comprehension, spoken production, reading, and writing, all applied in real-life communicative situations.

This article explores in depth the developmental pathway of communicative competence through CI, structured around the conceptual framework proposed by Trevor Doyle (2011) and the principle of contextualisation-decontextualisation-recontextualisation (CDR). Its aim is to propose an integrated pedagogical framework that provides effective resources for preparing learners to communicate authentically and adaptively in a globalised world.

2. Theoretical Foundations

Contextualised Instruction, as a paradigm that promotes the acquisition and development of communication skills in authentic situations, provides a solid foundation for preparing individuals for an increasingly interconnected society. The proposed framework is grounded in the conceptual framework of student-centred learning, promoted by Trevor Doyle (Doyle, 2011), which highlights the active role of the learner in the learning process and represents a valuable conceptual and practical framework. It was initially designed to explore how foreign language learning can take place in real contexts, with an emphasis on authentic language use and the application of knowledge in concrete situations.

The present study extends Doyle's model (2011) by integrating additional components compatible with Contextualised Instruction, aiming to provide a comprehensive and updated perspective on the process of developing Communicative Competence. A central element of this framework is the principle of contextualisation-decontextualisation-recontextualisation (CDR), which recognises that learning knowledge and skills is a continuous and dynamic process, rather than a static accumulation.

The CDR principle structures the learning process into three distinct stages:

- **Contextualisation** - presenting and learning knowledge and skills within a specific and authentic context, directly relevant to a particular domain or situation. For example, in teaching English, this involves using realistic dialogues from everyday life or professional contexts.
- **Decontextualisation** - extracting knowledge from the specific context in which it was initially presented and reformulating it in a more abstract and general form, fostering the ability to generalise and apply it across different situations.

- **Recontextualisation** - reintegrating knowledge and skills into a new or different context, developing adaptability and the ability to use them practically in a variety of real-life situations.

Contextualisation provides a solid foundation for understanding; decontextualisation promotes abstract thinking; and recontextualisation develops the ability to apply knowledge in diverse and complex contexts-thus ensuring the real and sustainable applicability of the competences developed.

An essential theoretical tool in selecting and analysing teaching materials in Contextualised Instruction (CI) is the Context-Text model, part of the systemic functional theory based on the research of Michael Halliday. This model approaches language as a complete system for meaning-making, whose components function in relation to one another. It argues that language cannot be understood outside its context-setting, participants, gestures, and social interactions are integral parts of the context and influence both the use and interpretation of the message.

The Context-Text Model (Halliday & Hasan, 1985) illustrates the hierarchical and interconnected relationship between language and context within the systemic functional linguistic framework. According to the model, meaning is constructed across multiple levels, beginning with individual lexical items and extending through sentences and texts to broader social and cultural contexts. Language use is therefore understood not as isolated linguistic production, but as embedded in specific communicative situations shaped by participants, purposes, and wider sociocultural conventions.

Figure 1. The Context-Text Model (adapted from Halliday&Hasan, 1985)

Figure 1 presents Halliday's Context-Text Model, illustrating how meaning is constructed across interconnected linguistic and contextual layers. At the linguistic

level, words and phrases form sentences, which are organised into coherent texts through grammatical and structural features. Meaning is further shaped by the social context, including communicative purpose, participants, and interaction, as well as by the broader cultural context, which reflects social values and audience expectations. In English language teaching, the model highlights the importance of presenting language within authentic communicative contexts rather than as isolated linguistic forms.

Within the framework of Contextualised Instruction and the e-PAR model, this figure supports the idea that language learning and reflective educational practices should not focus exclusively on isolated linguistic forms. Instead, authentic materials and learning activities should reflect meaningful communicative situations and culturally relevant contexts. The model therefore provides a theoretical foundation for integrating contextual, social, and cultural dimensions into educational practice, particularly in digitally mediated and reflective learning environments.

3. The Comprehensive Cyclical Framework for Developing Communicative Competence in English through Contextualised Instruction

The proposed pathway for developing communicative competence through Contextualised Instruction is organised as a cyclical framework consisting of eight interdependent stages, each contributing to the gradual formation of a competent and autonomous English language user. The overall diagram of the pathway is presented below:

Figure 2. The Development Pathway of Communicative Competence through Contextualised Instruction (CI)

Figure 2 illustrates the conceptual pathway proposed for the development of communicative competence through Contextualised Instruction (CI). The model presents communicative competence as a dynamic and cyclical process supported by interconnected pedagogical stages, including the identification of learners' prior knowledge, the selection of meaningful texts and contexts, the formulation of learning intentions and success criteria, collaborative learning, learner autonomy, and continuous feedback and evaluation.

The circular structure of the model emphasises that communicative competence development does not occur linearly, but through continuous interaction between instructional stages. Learners may revisit previous phases according to communicative needs, contextual demands, learning progressions, and reflective practice. The framework also highlights the role of authentic contexts, student-centered learning, collaboration, and gradual responsibility transfer in fostering language acquisition and communicative performance.

Within the proposed educational framework, the model supports the integration of contextual, cognitive, and social dimensions of learning, contributing to the development of meaningful and sustainable communicative competence.

The first stage of the pathway consists of building a learner profile database, in response to three fundamental questions: *What do students know? What can students do? What do learners still need?* This stage involves diagnosing the existing level of Communicative Competence, providing the teacher with a clear picture of the starting point of the learning process. A detailed description of the level enables a deeper understanding of the learning context and underpins all subsequent pedagogical decisions.

The "focus on language" stage represents a crucial moment in the development of language skills. It involves providing meaningful input (authentic texts, discussions, audio-video materials, interaction with native speakers) appropriate to the students' proficiency level, as well as producing meaningful output, such as active participation in discussions, writing texts, presenting projects, or simulating real-life communication situations.

Language processing at this stage operates both top-down and bottom-up simultaneously. Top-down processing draws on contextual information to anticipate meaning, while bottom-up processing builds understanding from concrete linguistic elements (sounds, words, structures) towards overall comprehension. Jeremy Harmer emphasises that a contextualised approach allows learners to actively discover how language works, generating a genuine sense of intellectual achievement (Harmer, 2007).

Hossein Nassaji and Sandra Fotos (2011) demonstrate that brief, focused grammar awareness activities integrated before communicative tasks lead to significantly greater accuracy in language production. The terminology used by the teacher when explaining grammatical rules should be accessible to learners, and the first language (L1) may be used strategically as a pedagogical tool. As Nassaji and Fotos (2011) conclude, L1 is an important pedagogical and social tool in foreign language contexts and can enhance target language learning.

Figure 3. The Balance between Input and Output in Language Learning

Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between meaningful input, meaningful output, and authentic language learning within the process of communicative competence development. The model emphasises that effective language acquisition depends on the balanced interaction between receptive and productive language activities.

The left side of the figure represents meaningful input, referring to learners' authentic exposure to language through texts, audio materials, discussions, multimedia resources, and contextualised communicative situations. This stage supports comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and the development of linguistic awareness. This stage uses learning progressions to identify specific intentions, operationalised through the questions: What understanding and receptive skills will be central? What productive skills will be targeted? Learning intentions and success criteria are defined based on the SMART framework developed by Doran (1981) (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound), ensuring clarity, measurability, and relevance for all participants in the educational process. The right side represents meaningful output, which involves the active use of language through speaking, writing, interaction, and collaborative communication tasks. Productive language use enables learners to apply acquired knowledge in authentic communicative contexts.

At the centre of the model is authentic language learning, which emerges from the continuous interaction between input and output processes. The figure highlights that deep understanding and communicative competence are developed when learners are actively engaged both in receiving and producing meaningful language within relevant social and educational contexts.

Within the Contextualised Instruction framework, the balance between input and output supports learner-centred communication, reflective learning, and the integration of authentic communicative experiences into language education.

Developing a learning plan aligned with these intentions-including lessons, activities, resources, and assessments-must be complemented by continuous monitoring of progress, adjusting the plan according to students' needs, and transparent communication of objectives at the beginning of the course. Flexibility and adaptability are essential, as each group of learners presents distinct needs.

The effective selection of texts in Contextualised Instruction is essential for the quality of the learning process. The main selection criteria include: relevance to learning objectives, appropriateness to students' proficiency level, diversity of text types (articles, stories, essays, dialogues, poems, literary extracts), cultural relevance and topicality, as well as interactivity and potential for discussion.

Brian Tomlinson encourages the use of authentic texts and tasks, while also recognising the value of activities that draw learners' attention to specific language features (Tomlinson, 2011). Rafał Duda and Henry Tyne (2010) highlight that authentic materials can be challenging for lower-level learners, requiring preparatory "chained activities". David Nunan warns that an overuse of simulated texts may hinder learning, advocating instead for the frequent use of authentic materials in EFL classrooms (Nunan, 1998).

A distinct category is represented by multimodal texts-combining written text, images, sound, video, and animation-which have significant potential for diversifying learning styles, recreating authentic situations, and deepening content understanding. The use of multimodal texts facilitates contextualisation and contributes to the development of students' critical thinking (Jewitt, 2008; Djonov, 2015). Moreover, as stated by Lim (2025) multimodal pedagogies can enrich language learning by enabling teachers to strategically orchestrate various semiotic resources to support understanding, engagement, and authentic communication, particularly in multilingual and linguistically diverse classrooms. One more important component is the integration of digital resources in EFL classrooms, which enables students to engage in authentic language practice across receptive and productive skills while receiving personalised support and feedback (Alzahrani et al., 2024)

Connecting to relevant prior knowledge creates cognitive bridges that facilitate the anchoring of new concepts. Marzano Robert (2004) argues that activating prior expertise significantly enhances the ability to process new information, while Campbell Linda and Campbell Bruce (2009) demonstrate that individuals with rich domain knowledge analyse multiple perspectives more effectively and arrive at more reasoned conclusions. Revisiting prior knowledge builds a solid foundation for new learning experiences and supports learners' self-esteem. Hattan et al. (2023) argue that activating prior knowledge helps students make sense of new texts by connecting new information to existing cognitive structures.

Recommended tools for activating prior knowledge:

• **K-W-L chart (What I know / What I want to know / What I have learned)** - enables quick assessment of prior knowledge, formulation of questions, and reflection on new learning.

• **Anticipation guides** - encourage students to reflect, write, and discuss opinions on key topics in the unit of study, based on statements they must agree or disagree with.

• **Multimedia resources** - watching a relevant video or a slide presentation before starting a new unit facilitates familiarisation with the context and terminology.

This stage integrates two complementary methodological frameworks: the Whole-Part-Whole (WPW) model and the REACT strategy (Relating, Experiencing, Applying, Cooperating, Transferring).

The WPW model, situated within the contextual framework, structures learning experiences into three stages: (1) presenting a global context or an authentic communicative task (*Whole*), providing an overview and motivating understanding of the purpose; (2) breaking down the competence into analysable components- vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, communication strategies (*Part*); (3) returning to the global context and applying the newly developed skills in an integrated way (*Whole*). Swanson H. Lee and Law Bryan (1993) argue that through the application of WPW, learners' understanding evolves from simple "knowledge" to "wisdom" (Swanson & Law, 1993).

Figure 4 demonstrates how the Whole-Part-Whole model supports contextualised language learning by enabling students to move from a global understanding of communicative situations toward detailed language analysis and subsequent reintegration into authentic use.

Figure 4. The Whole-Part-Whole (WPW) Model (after Swanson & Law, 1993)

The REACT strategy (Crawford, 2001) structures the learning pathway through five dimensions: *Relating* (preparing for learning and raising awareness of the relevance of communication in L2); *Experiencing* (exploring topics and

communication contexts); *Applying* (internalising competences through practical activities); *Cooperating* (practising the language in authentic communicative contexts through interaction with peers); *Transferring* (adaptively using skills in varied and new situations).

Collaboration among students plays an essential role in the development of language competences: it promotes peer learning, authentic practice of speaking and listening, improvement of writing and reading skills, stimulation of critical thinking, and the development of social and cultural competences necessary in a globalised world. In addition, collaborative activities create meaningful opportunities for learner interaction and language production in ESL/EFL settings. Richards highlights that role play is particularly effective in promoting learner-to-learner conversational interaction, as it enables students to engage in authentic communication and use language purposefully in context (Richards, Panahi & Mohebbi, 2023).

A fundamental objective of Contextualised Instruction is transforming the student from a passive participant into an active and responsible agent of their own learning. The Gradual Release of Responsibility (GRR) model-summarised in the phrase “I do, we do, you do”-describes a sequence of activities through which responsibility is gradually transferred from teacher to learner. Doug Buehl (2005) states that GRR “emphasises instruction that guides students to become capable thinkers and learners” (Buehl, 2005).

The GRR model involves four core phases: direct instruction (modelling), guided instruction (supported practice), collaborative learning, and independent practice. The ultimate goal is learner autonomy and the ability to transfer understanding to new contexts.

Figure 5 illustrates the progressive transfer of responsibility from teacher to learner. Within the proposed pathway, this model operationalises learner autonomy by gradually moving students from teacher-supported performance toward independent communicative competence.

Figure 5. The Gradual Release of Responsibility (GRR) Model (after Buehl, 2005)

The assessment and authentic feedback stage represents the final-yet at the same time cyclical-component of the development pathway of Communicative Competence. Authentic assessment employs methods focused on students' ability to use English in real-life situations: interviews, presentations, simulations, projects, and learning portfolios. As stated by Saeedi, Tajeddin & Tadayon (2025), in academic settings, where English serves both specific and general purposes, language assessment should be based on students' ability to use internationally recognised communicative forms of English effectively and appropriately in context. Consequently, assessment focuses not merely on linguistic accuracy, but on meaningful language use in authentic communicative situations.

Portfolios enable the documentation and self-evaluation of performance (audio/video recordings of conversations, essays, oral or written presentations). Self-assessment and peer assessment foster self-regulation skills and awareness of one's strengths and weaknesses. Teacher feedback is detailed and multidimensional-addressing not only grammatical accuracy, but also clarity of message, pronunciation, fluency, and listening skills-guiding students toward concrete and sustained improvement.

Assessment is a continuous process: the cycle of evaluation and feedback is repeated, contributing to the progressive development of communicative competence and to learners' confidence in their ability to communicate in authentic contexts.

The proposed pathway represents an integrated approach, bringing together principles from applied linguistics (Halliday, 1985; Nunan, 1998), socio-constructivist learning theory (Lev Vygotsky-ZPD, MKO), and learner-centred language pedagogy (Tomlinson, 2011; Nassaji & Fotos, 2011; Harmer, 2007). The cyclical nature of the model reflects the dynamic character of communicative competence development: not a linear process, but a recursive one, in which each cycle consolidates and extends previous learning.

The integration of multimodal texts and authentic materials, alongside strategies for activating prior knowledge, makes the approach both motivating and culturally relevant. The Gradual Release of Responsibility (GRR) model ensures progression from teacher dependence to full learner autonomy-one of the central aims of modern pedagogy.

A recurring challenge identified in the literature is managing the difficulty of authentic materials at lower proficiency levels. The proposed solution is the introduction of "chained activities" (Duda & Tyne, 2010), which prepare learners' gradual access to authentic materials while maintaining the necessary balance between difficulty and motivation.

4. Evaluating the Proposed Contextual Pathway in English Language Instruction

To explore the effectiveness of the proposed contextual pathway in English language instruction, a pilot quasi-experimental study was conducted with second-year English-major students at "Ion Creangă" State Pedagogical University of Chisinau and used a test/re-test design with a control group and an experimental group. The control

group was taught through a traditional grammar-focused approach, while the experimental group was instructed through a context-based approach over one semester. The findings showed stronger progress in the experimental group, especially in productive grammatical skills, fluency, control of grammatical structures, error correction and intelligibility of oral and written answers.

The *aim* of the pilot case study was to examine whether the proposed pathway for developing communicative competence through contextual instruction can support students' ability to use English more accurately, fluently and appropriately in authentic communicative situations.

The study was based on the following *hypothesis*: It was hypothesised that students exposed to instruction organised according to the proposed contextual pathway would demonstrate greater improvement in communicative competence than students taught through traditional grammar-focused instruction, particularly in terms of meaningful language use, fluency, accuracy, interaction, and ability to transfer language to new contexts.

The study involved second-year students majoring in English at "Ion Creangă" State Pedagogical University. The students were at approximately B2 level. Two academic groups were involved: one control group, taught through a traditional approach, and one experimental group, taught through contextual instruction.

Methodology. The research followed a phases of test/re-test design. Both groups completed a phase of test measuring components of grammatical accuracy and communicative performance. The test assessed grammatical knowledge, grammatical skills, receptive skills, productive skills and grammatical awareness.

During the treatment stage, the control group was taught mainly through explicit explanation, isolated examples and controlled grammar exercises. In contrast, the experimental group followed the proposed contextual pathway. The instruction included authentic input, guided discovery, meaningful output, collaboration, digital tools, oral and written production tasks, and authentic assessment.

The implementation of the proposed pathway included several interconnected stages. Initially, students' prior knowledge and communicative needs were identified through diagnostic assessment. Grammar structures were then introduced through authentic or semi-authentic communicative contexts: Students' prior knowledge and needs were identified through the phase of test; Grammar was introduced through authentic or semi-authentic texts and communicative situations; Students were informed what language functions and communicative outcomes they were expected to achieve; Texts, videos and tasks were selected according to students' level and communicative needs; Students connected the target structures to previous experience and familiar contexts; Students moved from whole context to language analysis and back to communicative use, following the Whole-Part-Whole logic; Students worked in pairs and groups to produce spoken and written responses; Students completed oral and written tasks, received teacher and peer feedback, and reflected on their progress.

During the research study were used the following **methods and instruments**: oral and written production tasks; teacher observation; student work samples; digital

tools for practice and assessment, such as Wizer.me, Quizizz, Kahoot, LearningApps, Vocaroo, Flipgrid, Screencastify, Storyjumper and Bookcreator.

Results-discussion integrated. The findings indicate that both groups demonstrated measurable progress following instruction; however, the contextual instruction group achieved substantially stronger gains across most assessed dimensions.

Figure 6. Test and retest results regarding the development of grammatical and communicative performance in the control group (points)

The most notable improvement was observed in productive grammatical skills and grammatical awareness. Students in the experimental group became more fluent, demonstrated better control of basic and complex structures, corrected their errors more confidently and produced more intelligible oral and written answers. The study showed an increase of 1.5 points in productive grammatical skills and 1.4 points in receptive grammatical skills in the experimental group.

Figure 7. Test and retest results regarding the development of grammatical and communicative performance in the experimental group (points)

The added value of the proposed framework lies in its integrative and cyclical nature. While previous approaches to communicative competence development have frequently focused on isolated pedagogical dimensions, such as authentic materials,

contextual learning, grammar awareness, or learner autonomy, the present framework brings together these elements into a coherent developmental pathway.

More specifically, the proposed model contributes to the field in several ways. First, it integrates the contextualisation–decontextualisation–recontextualisation (CDR) principle with complementary pedagogical models, including Whole-Part-Whole (WPW), the REACT strategy, and the Gradual Release of Responsibility (GRR), within a single operational structure. Second, unlike more fragmented approaches, the framework conceptualises communicative competence development as a cyclical and recursive process rather than a linear progression.

Third, the model explicitly connects contextualised instruction with authentic assessment, learner autonomy, multimodal texts, and prior knowledge activation, thereby offering teachers a practical and pedagogically coherent framework for planning, implementing, and evaluating English language instruction in higher education contexts.

Consequently, the proposed pathway contributes not only theoretically, by systematising previously disconnected pedagogical concepts, but also practically, by offering a transferable model adaptable to diverse English language teaching contexts.

5. Conclusions

This article proposes a comprehensive cyclical framework for developing Communicative Competence in English through Contextualised Instruction, articulating eight interdependent stages integrated through the CDR principle and supported by validated pedagogical models: Whole-Part-Whole, REACT, and the Gradual Release of Responsibility.

The development pathway of communicative competence through Contextualised Instruction provides teachers with concrete tools to plan, implement, and evaluate the teaching-learning process of English, ensuring that students not only acquire linguistic knowledge but also develop the ability to apply it effectively in authentic and diverse contexts. Thus, the communicative competence acquired becomes a real resource for personal and professional success in contemporary globalised society.

The study has several *limitations*, including the relatively small sample size and the short duration of the intervention. Future research may involve longitudinal implementation across different educational contexts and proficiency levels to further prove its applicability and effectiveness.

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